

Monitoring of OH Transmission Lines

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Summary

The monitoring of overhead line has become an essential part of operating transmission systems in the past few decades. In some countries, it is already a standard tool for managing energy flow while others monitor the grid elements to improve the efficiency or safety of the utilized line. The practical examples of the methods are proven over the years in many countries. This has core importance because utilities prefer to, enhance reliability, and optimize energy flow according to different weather situations and reduce the cost of the operation. To implement this kind of optimized system, dynamic line rating could be an optional, but not the only smart method. The article presented is intended to review the general methods applied for monitoring the overhead transmission lines. Even with the best intention, it is not possible to cover all the methods and devices available in the market but this summary aims to outline the present challenges on the topic. The issue of the paper includes the monitoring of conductor clearance, sag, conductor temperature, the process of ice detection and de-icing methods applying mathematical models, weather information along the overhead lines and also field imaging. Besides describing technologies, short examples and analyses are provided through the gathered data over the years while conducting monitoring projects.

Index Terms — dynamic line rating, sag, clearance, ice detection, wind speed, line section, on-line monitoring, static thermal rating

1. Introduction

In many countries, the pace of investment in OHLs (overhead lines) has lagged behind the rate of load growth and generated additional capacities, due to public, regulatory, environmental, and financial obstacles to the construction of new transmission facilities. Consequently, many OHLs reached critical values of load and sag posing new challenges for the system operators. Many renewable energy sources, especially hydro plants, solar, or wind farms also require the dynamic operation of the power grid. A lot of industrial application is about implementing a so-called “energy management”, where the monitoring of energy consumption and all kinds of inputs such as gas, electrical energy, water, harmonics, etc., are measured just to manage and to achieve the highest possible cost-effective production while minimizing costs and maintaining the level of reliability. But in the end, even these companies require from a utility a stable and permanent energy supply to manage the production and save costs during their optimization. In the past, utilities have invested a lot in substation monitoring, protection systems, etc. but one of the most important parts of the energy system is also the conductor on overhead lines, which is limiting power transfer from one substation to another. At the same time utilities are under continuous pressure for optimizing the performance of the network and to reduce costs (OPEX & CAPEX) while enhancing or maintaining the availability and reliability. Monitoring of OH transmission lines have many benefits besides monitoring and operation, it can be used for maintenance optimization, optimization of energy transfer – dynamic line rating (DLR), and maintenance. Monitoring systems help utilities not to overload OH transmission lines and at another time when weather conditions are favourable and if required, they can add additional load to existing lines, without jeopardizing the safety of the OH transmission line operating regulations.

2. Why is it important to monitor OH Transmission Lines?

Overhead lines are the backbone of the electrical power transmission system and they can be easily stated to be also the backbone of any countries power supply. In most cases, an overhead line is the most economic and practicable solution for energy transmission. On the other hand, the energy consumption in Europe and the US is growing and the volatility of transmitted power is also increasing during the last decade caused by the opening of the electric energy market. The operators of transmission lines are forced to ensure the electrical power supply so they must improve the reliability of the network. One solution is to monitor the critical (heavily loaded) overhead lines. For example, with the knowledge of the thermal condition, the risk of unexpected outages can be reduced. Today several monitoring systems are available on the market and they differ in the principle and techniques. Besides growing energy consumption, the rapid growth of renewable energy cannot be neglected. The pace of renewable energy keeps accelerating. Rapid cost reductions for solar and wind power have put these technologies as primary of the energy transformation. To manage the impact of redistributed energy sources, while maintaining low electricity costs, more flexible and resilient power systems are required. In Europe, investment in monitoring and managing renewable energy is now starting to move in the direction of monitoring.

As the utilities must manage large-scale integration of renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic and wind energy, it can be done effectively only if system operators have the necessary tools to handle their inherent variability. TSOs are now testing emerging power technologies to increase system flexibility and develop suitable market models allowing small scale, widely distributed resources, such as storage devices and demand response units, to provide flexibility services (especially in light of further transport electrification).ⁱ

3. Components of a monitoring system

Reviewing the populous collection of relevant articles, it can be found that the Electrical Power Research Institute published a study with the title: Future Inspection of Overhead lines, in 2008. Within this study, there are already listed possible solutions for the instrumented tower: Optical image sensing, Infrared image sensing, Ultraviolet Image Sensing, Satellite Image Sensing, LIDAR, Vibration Sensing, Acoustic Sensing, Strain Sensing, Tilt Sensing, Magnetostrictive Sensing (MsS), Ultrasonic Sensing, Direct Contact Temperature Sensing, and many more. ii Probably, the list of potential solutions is much longer, and it partially depends on utility preferences and investments. In general three types of a monitoring system can be defined:

- Indirect monitoring (non- contact) system,
- Direct monitoring (contact to the conductor or tower) system,
- Combination of indirect and direct systems.

With indirect monitoring, the observation within the OH transmission corridor is achieved without physical contact with the tower or the conductor. With indirect monitoring the following groups can be defined:

- Weather station: in the vicinity of the OH transmission lines (it is preferred to apply weather stations on the towers because it reflects the exact wind speed and wind direction that is influencing the conduct or behaviour). With weather station data and the ampacity formula of CIGREⁱⁱⁱ, IEEE or inhouse development, the utility can calculate ampacity and wind influence on overhead lines
- Vegetation management: By knowing how fast the vegetation is growing along the transmission line, the utilities can prepare for cleaning (cutting) the vegetation along the overhead line's corridors in advance. This can prevent future unexpected faults. Besides special software, this can be done by helicopter or even satellite.^{iv} (For example, the algorithms discern if sections of an overhead line routed through a dense forest encounter a clearing, or if the vegetation close to the overhead line consists of small bushes or large trees. They also identify the positions where vegetation is growing too close to the overhead line. The models are also able to classify the

composition of the vegetation surrounding the overhead line, but different tree species pose varying levels of threat to the overhead line, which often needs to be factored into a risk analysis).

- Laser scanning: With the laser scanner data (helicopter or ground), it is possible to analyse the exact 3D location of power transmission line (TL) structures and objects in surrounding areas.^v
- Thermal camera: with a thermal camera, utilities are checking the “hot spots” of the overhead lines. A thermal camera can be used with line workers or helicopter thermal scanning that is normally in combination with corona video/pictures.

Direct methods of OH transmission line monitoring

With direct methods, physical contact with the conductor or the tower is referred. This monitoring equipment can add accuracy and enhance security for dynamic line rating of overhead lines, as it is summarized in the following:

- Conductor temperature: while considering the safety margins it is obvious that the key information is the conductor temperature. However, it needs to be considered, that the same temperature of the conductor results in a completely different current situation in the winter or summer periods. The current conductor temperature alerts the operator when it approaches the temperature limit because it takes into account momentarily influences (current, wind, sun radiation) that reflect on the line temperature.^{vi}
- Sag, clearance: All three “measurements” link to the same issue – if the conductor is close to its maximal temperature limit, it can violate the sag or clearance limit. Quite a few companies already offer the measurement of sag and clearance. Determining the actual line geometry is very useful that supports dynamic line rating.
- Tower vibrations: Besides measuring the conductor temperature, conductor vibrations, forces in the conductor, etc., it needs to be considered that all stated is reflecting on the towers. With tower vibration measurement, utilities can define over a longer period whether the towers are overdesigned or under-designed, and how all conditions (temperature, ice, wind) are influencing as a function of the tower's lifetime.
- Camera: like many times stated pictures can describe more than a thousand words, the camera, and artificial intelligence can help utilities to confirm a lot of situations on the side like ice, galloping, and possible fire within the OH transmission line corridor.

Figure 1 Combination of the direct and indirect method for dynamic line rating

4. Monitoring supported services

Besides the installation of the equipment and installation of all different software, there are always supporting activities to establish monitoring of OH transmission lines:

- Analyzing the transmission line: many times, the utilities can determine with analysis where the monitoring devices can work most efficiently. In other cases, external consulting companies are hired for these purposes. To implement efficient monitoring with a DLR-based complex

transmission grid management system it is essential to select the proper transmission lines for the sensor installation. The success of transmission line selection can be ensured by a complex, multi-criteria-based analytical process. A successful DLR-based system can only be the basis for a comprehensive transmission line management system that can effectively provide higher transmission capacity limits and a more resilient grid while maintaining the existing level of security.

- **Modelling:** The first step in determining the installation place of the sensors on the power line is to perform a critical span analysis of the transmission line. In this process, the position of the catenary curve of the lower phase conductor at the maximum allowable conductor temperature is determined by modelling-based sag simulation. The algorithm also considers the elevation profile and objects under the line (e.g.: intersections, buildings, railway overhead lines, etc.), based on which the value of the clearance reserve is determined for each tension and each suspension spans. With the knowledge of the clearance reserve, the number of the required sensors and their installation placement is determined, which adequately represents the entire observed transmission line. Installing the sensor into the critical span ensures that, if the standard criteria for the clearance reserves are met at these spans, compliance with the standards is ensured along the entire power line.

Figure 2 Real-time sag and clearance modelling in a grid management system

- **Software:** Besides using the direct or indirect method, one of the most important solutions in OH transmission line monitoring is the software background. Software algorithms can be used for interpretation of measurement data with the connection to the grid operator – the SCADA system. Developed algorithms are more and more efficient adding information that could be missed only by monitoring the raw data.
- **Other supporting activities:** All system direct or indirect require support. In the case of sensors installed on a transmission, line utility should take into account at least firmware and software updates that are necessarily caused by security or new development.

5. Examples of data monitoring in the vicinity of OH transmission lines

In this chapter, a few possibilities are described where monitoring of OHL Transmission lines provides additional value to existing or new infrastructures. At this point, it is important to mention that there could be other possible solutions in addition to this presented example.

Ampacity

Ampacity is defined as the maximum current, in amperes, that a conductor can carry continuously under the conditions of use without exceeding its temperature rating limit value. This expression covers the current-carrying capacity of the conductor. The ampacity of a conductor depends on its ability to dissipate heat without damage to the conductor or its insulation. This is a function of the insulation temperature rating, the electrical resistance of the conductor material, the ambient temperature, and the ability of the insulated conductor to dissipate heat to the surrounds.”^{vii} All over the world, OHL’s transfer capacity is still calculated based on the conventional thermal equilibrium of the conductor. Under steady-state circumstances, some factors heat (Joule-heating, solar radiation heat, etc.) while others cool down (convective cooling, radiative cooling, precipitation, etc.) the conductor. By knowing the environmental and load parameters the conductor temperature can be calculated via physical and analytical methods. All the OHL has a maximum allowable temperature value that cannot be exceeded to avoid sag and material degradation problems of the conductor. This maximum strict temperature determines the ampacity limit of a given OHL.

A simple and most widespread ampacity calculation method is the so-called static line rating (SLR). In the case of SLR, the ampacity of the line is calculated according to the worst-case scenario of the environmental parameters. This means that the result of the calculation is for the warmest summer day with slight wind speed and without precipitation, which represents the transfer capacity of the OHL for the whole year. This method provides the safe operation of the network, but economically not optimized. Moreover, the opportunities of OHLs are not exploited and other ampacity calculation methods are appreciating due to the increasing electricity demand.^{viii}

While building a new power line has not just a high investment cost but a strict legal environment and social resistance, the ways and means of managing the power output on the existing lines are becoming extremely critical. Sometimes, enhancing power transmission capacity in the same corridor takes many years due to the non-availability of shut down and right of way sensitivity.^{ix} Using sensors or mathematical models to increase the capacity of the transmission lines is in general much faster and cheaper, but the generation and consumption always must be considered. By adjusting the ampacity limit to the changes of the weather parameter, the utilities can have information to make appropriate decisions on the load of the line if necessary. This is the core sense of applying the dynamic line rating method. The conductor temperature of the line varies due to weather conditions like wind direction, wind speed, solar radiation, etc. The classical static line rating which is generally used for load planning of the line is based on ambient temperature, solar radiation and wind speed conditions. This is a condition, which is not entirely relevant throughout the year. As an example, in tropical countries such as India, it is important to measure the real-time temperature of the line to have information about the possibility of increasing or decreasing its loading.^x

Figure 3 Line current, line temperature, and Ampacity^{xi}

Ampacity prediction

The prediction of ampacity (or DLR – dynamic line rating) is essential to have information on the transfer capacity of the line for the future. The forecasted ampacity can be useful for system operators in day-ahead scheduling and market issues also. Comparing predicted circuit loads to forecast ratings allows the utility to plan outages, maintenance, and assure system load reliability. Forecast line ratings are calculated based on forecast weather conditions.^{xiii} The more accurate the weather prediction, the more accurate is the rating of the OH transmission line. As any meteorologist affirms, forecasting air temperature and solar heating is relatively straightforward, and the accuracy is quite high whereas forecasting wind speed and direction within a transmission line corridor is relatively complex and is typically less precise. To add precision to forecasts, utilities are linking weather station measurements (ambient temperature, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, precipitation, and sometimes even hail) with prediction models from commercial weather service that runs their models every hour. If the line ratings are to be adjusted hourly rather than daily, the prediction of air temperature is more accurate and variation minimum. At this point it must be emphasized, that a lot of meteorological models are evolving rapidly – and as additional measurements are available, the more greater the accuracy.

Figure 4 Real-time and forecasted ampacity

Line rating predictions require dedicated weather forecasts. According to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are roughly ten operational Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models for the global domain, i.e. covering the whole world, running with horizontal resolutions between 15 and 40 km (e.g. IFS from ECMWF in Europe, GFS from NOAA in the USA). For smaller domains, typically a few thousand kilometres in each direction, LAMs (Limited Area Models) run with a horizontal resolution of a few kilometres (e.g. WRF, ALADIN, HIRLAM, COSMO). They are, however, dependent on forecasts from global models at the boundaries of their domains, and so is in part their accuracy.

Sag/Clearance

Sag and clearance are two variables that are dependent on conductor temperature, varying with conductor current and ambient conditions. Sag can be determined in many ways such as inclination measurement, vibrations, laser measurement, or based on mathematical models, too. However, it is important to notice, that mathematical models use the ideal elastic flexibility without inner friction. This assumption simplifies the calculation and the OHL span is presented as a free moving conductor, whose length changes following ambient conditions like gravity, wind, ice, and sun. By implementing additional measurements (such as

inclination, vibration, or laser), the mathematical model has higher accuracy. For higher sag accuracy, it is preferred to do conductor site measurements of the catenary, which is especially important for old OH transmission lines in order to investigate the ageing effect on the sag.

Figure 5 Catenary measurement scheme of an OHL span

Icing/De-icing

The icing of the OHL's is an unpleasant phenomenon that may cause serious damages in the grid by forming extra mechanical load on the conductors. The renovation of the collapsed high voltage tower is extremely costly not to mention the problems of the lack of energy supply and availability. Besides the geometry of the conductor, local environmental conditions, such as rainfall, ambient temperature, humidity, wind speed, and direction, also play an important role in the formation of an ice layer on the surface of the conductors. These parameters determine the structural properties of the resulting ice layer and thus its properties. Based on these environmental factors, three types of ice can be distinguished, which can cause a high mechanical load to the conductors through high-adhesion and density.^{xiii} Ice formation on OHLs can cause serious damage in the grid by forming extra mechanical load on the conductors. The restoration of the collapsed high voltage towers is extremely costly not to mention the problems of the lack of energy supply. Several international models are available for modelling and predicting the icing of transmission line conductors. Based on the weather parameters given by the weather forecast and the expected temperature of the conductor, the algorithm determines the probability of the formation of an ice layer on the surface of the phase conductors during the observed period.

De-Icing

The extended ampacity limit of the power line applying the DLR method is not just favourable for higher current capacity in case of congestion problems, but also for avoiding unpleasant icing events in the vicinity of the OHL. If the ampacity limit is higher, higher currents can flow that results in higher Joule-heats, which consequently heat the conductors. If limits can be reached or approached, icing can be prevented. If prevention is not possible, the detection and removal of the ice layer is necessary. The proper handling of icing issues requires advanced algorithms (expert systems) and reliable measuring equipment.

Adding sensors to measure the temperature of the conductor is also useful, because if the conductor temperature is higher than 2 °C, then the ice layer cannot form on the conductor.

Figure 6 Collapse of high voltage towers as the result of an icing event

De-icing is combining knowledge about icing, sag, and temperature measurement. To calculate the current necessary to remove the ice layer, Joule heating - convective heat transfer and melting of ice must be taken into account. Since Joule heating represents the dominant mechanism, convection and radiation are neglected. Specific thermal capacity is considered for each separate material. The necessary temperature that is needed to heat the conductor and the ice build-up from $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and to transform ice into liquid water is obtained by calculating the mass of the steel core conductor, Al-stripes and ice. If the ice build-up stopped at the time of a current increase, the time needed for the ice to melt is presented in Figure 7. The red line shows the result for the maximum current that is allowed by the HV equipment in the overhead power field (e.g. disconnector, break-switch, measuring transformers), i.e. 800 A. This line shows the shortest possible time for the removal of the ice from the conductor by increasing the current.

To calculate the current necessary to remove the ice build-up, Joule heating, solar radiation, radiation of the conductor surface, convective heat transfer and melting of water have to be taken into account. Since Joule heating represents the dominant mechanism, convection and radiation shall be neglected in further calculations. Specific thermal capacity (c_{Fe} , c_{Al} , c_{i}) has to be considered for each separate material.

The heat needed to heat the conductor and ice build-up from $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the transformation of ice into liquid water is obtained by calculating the mass of the steel core, conductor, Al-stripes and ice per unit length of the conductor.

The heat of conductor per unit length is in balance with specific electric resistance per unit length, and therefore can be written as:

$$\frac{Q}{l} = \frac{R}{l} \cdot I^2 \cdot t \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) by rearranging gives the required current, by considering specific heat and specific electric resistance in given time of heating according to (2).

$$I^2 = \frac{Q/l}{R/l \cdot t} = \quad (2)$$

The required current also can be written by the following equation:

$$I = \sqrt{\frac{1}{t \cdot R} [A_{Fe} \cdot \rho_{Fe} \cdot c_{Fe} \cdot \Delta T + A_{Al} \cdot \rho_{Al} \cdot c_{Al} \cdot \Delta T + \rho_i \cdot \pi((r + \delta_i)^2 - r^2) \cdot (q_i + c_i \cdot \Delta T)]} \quad (3)$$

where

- (R/l) – the specific resistance of conductor [Ω/m],
- c_{Fe} – the specific thermal capacity of steel [$J/(K \cdot kg)$],
- c_{Al} – the specific thermal capacity of aluminium [$J/(K \cdot kg)$],
- c_i – the specific thermal capacity of ice [$J/(K \cdot kg)$],
- ρ_{Fe} – specific mass density of steel [kg/m^3],
- ρ_{Al} – specific mass density of aluminium [kg/m^3],
- ρ_i – specific mass density of ice [kg/m^3],
- q_i – specific melting heat of ice [J/kg],
- δ_i – thickness of ice [m],
- A_{Fe} – surface section of steel [m^2],
- A_{Al} – surface section of aluminium [m^2],
- ΔT – conductor temperature below zero [K],
- t – time [s].

To obtain the equation (3) the temperature dependence of metal resistivity and electrical conductivity of the ice was also neglected. The current as a function of ice melting time for various thicknesses of ice on the ACSR 240/40 mm² conductor observed is calculated from the equation (3), as shown in Figure 7.

Under the assumption that the ice accretion stopped at the time of a current increase, the time needed for ice melting can be graphically read from Figure 7.

Figure 7 Speed of ice melting depending on ice thickness and current

A red line presents the result for the maximum current that is allowed by the high voltage equipment in the substation (e.g. disconnector, break-switch, measuring transformers), i.e. 800 A. The intersection of this curve with the ice thickness-dependent melting curve presents the shortest possible time for the elimination of the ice from the conductor by an increase in the current. ^{XIV}

Camera

The camera's added value is significant, especially if the measurement is uncertain or while checking the transmission line is easier than site check. Cameras can be installed on the tower or on the conductor so the utility can see what is happening on the conductor or the towers. Figure 8 and Figure 9 are showing some field imaging taken by line monitoring sensors camera.

Figure 8 Field imaging during normal circumstances

Figure 9 Ice detection with the use of camera

Tower vibration measurements

The goal with tower vibration measurement is to foster the asset management system by determining the health of the tower and expected operation time that can be quickly shortened by ambient conditions, conductor influence or vandalism. In the article, academic findings are presented during the two years of operation on a high voltage tower.

With enough number of loading, cycles are possible to monitor vibration behaviour and frequencies of the selected tower. ^{xvi, xvii} The left illustration of Figure 10 shows the acceleration RMS parameters for both accelerometers (ACC1 and ACC2). It can be seen that the highest vibration occurred at ACC1 device in the direction of conductor orientation while in a perpendicular direction (ACC2) the vibration is lower. However, both the highest amplitude appeared at the same time, which can be mainly influenced by the meteorological conditions (wind, temperature and rain).

By analysing the frequency gathered over one month measurement period for both accelerometers, the distribution of natural frequencies can be determined based on FPT analysis, as it is shown on the right side of Figure 10. The illustration of the right side of Figure 10 shows that the most intensive frequency occurred on several levels during the one-month observation. Each level corresponds to a different order of natural frequencies of the tower. The natural frequencies are 4.39 Hz, 6.05 Hz, 7.03 Hz, 11.43 Hz, 13.67 Hz, 25.39 Hz and 29.88 Hz for 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th order, respectively. It can be said this order of natural frequency is a unique “identification card” of the tower. If this order is going to change in the long term, it means that the tower’s profile bounds or something else has been changed and TSO personnel should check the tower conditions.

Figure 10 Acceleration RMS parameters for both accelerometers ACC1 and ACC2 during one month period (left) and Natural (“Eigen”) frequency distribution as results of FPT analysis for demo tower (right)

Natural frequencies results provide several loading cycles for the different amplitude of stress. It means that based on the measured stress in the tower’s legs, the utilization rate of the tower under regular operating conditions can be estimated. Measured stresses in each tower leg vary with temperature and with meteorological conditions (wind, rain) and as well as the mechanical behaviour of the tower. Due to the monitoring of vibrations, it is possible to obtain natural frequency characteristic of the tower, the so-called ID of the tower and it will also be possible to detect changes in the behaviour of the tower through different temperature conditions, as well as in case of more pronounced deviations, the possible loosening of the screw connections of profiles without a physical inspection of the selected tower.

6. IT security

With every monitoring system, we must take into account data security. In modern and complex DLR systems, good infrastructure planning and implementation is of essential value. The option to provide virtual or physical server is left to the utility decision but we must emphasise, that dedicated hosting servers provide high security, backup and fast figuration in case of failure. In the end, hosting architecture is always the decision of utility:

- Hosting at the utility infrastructure
- Hosting at the external provider

As dealing with constant live measurements from the line and with live calculation on the server, a minimum of 99,9% uptime and the response of the system is mandatory. To achieve this goal,

ISO27001 or equivalent system standard management is required to be implemented and used by the hosting provider.

Other tools that provide additional security of the data:

- Encryption of data at rest and transit
- Server and software tools hardening
- Software development security tests
- ISMS management policy integration
- Events management system

Measured and calculated data needs to be stored in secure databases. Mostly file encryption on the database location is provided. On modern systems, the database server is segregated from the configuration and analysis tools server. The communication with analysis tools (front end) standard is via Rest API calls. This approach provides a stable and comfortable use of analysis tools and additional security for the saved data to the database. Data presentation to the provided analysis tools is not the only way to read all the data. A modern DLR system can also export data for in-depth analysis.

Another option of the modern DLR system is to connect to the TSOs operators' team and their used tools:

- Classical IEC 60870-5-104 protocol for connection to SCADA is provided for implementation
- On-demand TASE/2 protocol for connection to SCADA
- Rest API calls to monitor live data on developed dashboards

7. Conclusions

Overhead lines are vital elements in the transmission system. By monitoring the actual state of the conductors higher utilization in power flow can be reached, while the operational safety also increases with the implementation of health monitoring system, or ice detection function of the realized expert system. We believe that the benefit to utilities is using the combination of direct and indirect measurements to measure as much as possible and to calculate when measurements are not economically or physically possible. From the investment side, it can be stated, that the implementation of an extensive expert system is much lower than building new high voltage lines. However, in this case, the surplus ampacity can exceed 30 % regarding the static line rating in average, while the mentioned additional advantages are also appearing (ice detection, field imaging, health monitoring, etc.). This paper provided insight into the state-of-the-art OHL monitoring techniques by summarizing their benefits.

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